

"Knowledge sharing as a Moderator between organizational learning and error management culture in Academic staff"

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ABSTRACT: The subject of this research is " knowledge sharing as a Moderator between organizational learning and error management culture in Academic staff " in this research, used research method is from kind of applied on baise of research aim and from kind of descriptive - correlation on baise of information collection ways statistics society to this research is include all employees in islamic azad unversity of Ardabil Branch in 2020. Statistics sample for this research is include 196 person from employees (128 man, 68 woman) in Islamic Azad University of Ardabil Branch according to Morgan's scheme. Therefore used sampling ways to this plann is stratified sampling. We used from Just Culture (JC) Questionnaire , Organizational Learning Questionnaire & Knowledge Sharing for this research. considering, Alpha factors are toward 1 and they are upper than 0.8, We can said that every 3 questionnaire have acceptable reality and validity. Based on the findings of the study, it can be said that the mediating role of knowledge sharing in the effect of error management culture on organizational learning of the staff of Ardabil Azad University is positive and significant. In this study, it was found that the culture of error management and knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on organizational learning and also the culture of error management has a positive effect on knowledge sharing. Also in this study, the culture of error management and organizational learning among the staff of Ardabil Branch of Azad University has a favorable situation, but the situation of knowledge sharing and each of its dimensions is not favorable in the study population. According to the research findings, it is suggested that organizational managers to promote organizational learning, to define and prepare programs to understand and establish a culture of error management among employees and in all organizational units to develop organizational knowledge sharing through this work. Used to increase the absorption of knowledge and organizational learning.

Keywords: Knowledge Sharing, Organizational Learning, Error Management Culture

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1. Introduction

In the studies we conducted on empirical research on the knowledge management of Iranian organizations, we clearly encountered little research. In contrast, research conducted in other countries shows that knowledge dissemination leads to improving the learning situation in organizations. In an organizational problem, in order to be able to solve that problem and learn from it, the members of the organization must be able to share their experiences and information with their colleagues, think about it and be able to put the components that are related to each other in a framework and learn the knowledge gained from it. In fact, organizational members can exchange their knowledge and learned experiences for practical application with their colleagues through the dissemination of knowledge, and by combining this information and experiences with previous knowledge to produce new knowledge. They can also evaluate their use of information by disseminating knowledge (Yang, 2007).

Organizational learning, which is influenced by the culture of error management and knowledge dissemination, is the first variable discussed in this research. This phenomenon raises the spirit of performance appraisal in the organization and provides the organization with expansion and customer orientation (Algreen et al., 2014, pp. 540-531). There are different definitions of learning in the organization, from which we can refer to the definition that 3 (1998, p. 16; quoted by Fathi Karkargh, 2020) which considered organizational learning as: the ability of the organization to implement and complete activities appropriate management structures, structures and procedures that facilitate and encourage learning.

Knowledge dissemination as a moderating variable and subscale of knowledge management is the second variable that is examined in this section. In its definition, it should be said that the knowledge dissemination process is one of the stages of knowledge management that divides and disseminates knowledge in the organization. Pays that members use them in solving organizational problems. Also, knowledge dissemination emphasizes the integration of culture with technology (Iqbal Sarai and Ismaili, 2007). Studies show that knowledge and information are the main focus of organizational change and form the basis of the global economy, and since it is necessary for today's organizations to improve their efficiency (Arpaki, 2017), organizations should consider the importance of knowledge distribution. Understand their performance and understand the value that this information and information acquires after sharing (Rigg, 2005, quoted by Mahdian Rad et al., 2017).

Error management culture is the third variable discussed in this study, which is considered as an important method or tool that organizations can use to adapt to their changing environmental conditions and in these dynamic and competitive conditions prevail. Meet the necessities of survival between organizations. Organizational Error Management Culture - can help organizations learn from their mistakes and deviations and behave effectively in the future with an emphasis on sharing knowledge and experience and managing mistakes. These experiences used in organizations, especially educational organizations, is one of the important and strategic resources that can be used in learning, innovation and survival in changing environmental situations, which this advantage will not be realized unless organizations have a management culture. Use error and in this way

reduce costs, develop the level of education and learning, prevent wastage of time. Provided the application of technology in services and..... (Moradi et al., 2012). There are various definitions of error management culture in organizations, for example, the definition of "error management culture is a culture in which the occurrence of organizational errors and mistakes is considered inevitable and organizational managers, employees who do not reprimand or blame the perpetrators for their mistakes (quoted by Moradi et al., 2013). Considering the above, the purpose of this study is to investigate and analyze the mediating role of knowledge sharing in the impact of error management culture on organizational learning of Academic staff.

The impact of education and learning on the fate of humanity is still an important issue for thinkers, and this is increasingly understood during the changes and transformations that have occurred in the scientific and cultural dimensions of the world and the complexities that surround human issues and communication. In fact, it is human beings who make their society and raw world better, and it is also education that makes skilled human beings, so we must pay attention to the quality and manner of education and training of human beings. Mizul paid special attention (Hesarbani, 2006) in the organizational field, staff growth in organizations such as educational organizations is achieved when the existing organizational relationships between employees are based on learning (Bush and Midwood, 2005, translated by Ahanchian and Atighi, 2014, p. 259). Due to the rapid changes in the environment and the changes that occur in individuals, the human need to be prepared to adapt to these changes, learning and access to facilities and strong techniques for progress in life, is obvious. Human beings, by thinking that they can learn more as a group (participatory learning) and achieve their goals more easily (Wallace, 2002), created organizations, groups and associations. In fact, this action is in line with the environment. External variable was performed. In this sense, organizations are considered as an "open system with thought and life". Emphasizing that organizations, like the human mind, rely on receiving feedback to adapt to changing environmental conditions; Organizations, like smarter animals and humans, can be said to learn from experience and engage in complex mental processes such as "predict, identify, define, design, and solve problems." Some theorists of "systems" and "contingency" approaches to organizations believe that "in many organizations, some forms of organizational learning occur on a regular basis"; Such as three common organizational learning processes, which are: activities to improve and develop annual resources, strategic planning activities, and the application and mastery of new technologies in the organization. However, organizations do not usually use all their talent and learning power. The result of learning an organization is the set of its components before the result of individual learning; That is, the result of learning the whole organization is more than the sum of individual learning and the channel of its constituent parts. Individual learning resulting from the training and development of human resources skills, the provision of scientific databases, and familiarity with new theories and frameworks only leads to organizational learning when it affects managerial initiatives, policies, and organizational design strategies.(Naderi et al., 2007).

Wherever in the world today, where human beings are at the center of movements, activities, and communications, there are errors and mistakes behind these actions, and their effects are manifested in their individual, organizational, and social lives. These effects are human responses. Affects external stimuli (and the quality of output products in the human-machine relationship). These matters can severely affect the individual and organizational performance of individuals (Brager et al., 2003). The past is more felt. In fact, the knowledge gained from mistakes and their learning is stored as a permanent and enduring source in individual and organizational memory, the value of which is higher than the knowledge gained from individual and organizational success. High value plays an important role in improving individual and organizational performance. Individual and organizational errors are the result of lack of awareness and knowledge deficiencies of

individuals in personal and organizational life. To be revised or changed has been more than ever in line with global developments and the expansion of efforts of educational systems to improve the quality of educational processes and activities, in scientific forums and educational policy-making wide-ranging discussions about the need for educational reform and improving the quality of educational services. Organization of the country's universities in Mia N officials, experts and experts of the educational and administrative system of the country have been designed. (Azizi and Heidari, 2012) Therefore, it can be pointed out that many organizations, including educational organizations, pay attention to the way of dealing with errors and mistakes or in general to the culture of error management (Van Dyke, 2005).

The development and progress of human civilization and the progress and growth of man in various fields has always been associated with trial, trial and error, the results of which can be seen in their performance in any field. While errors and mistakes are undesirable, but the number of mistakes made by people increases the amount of learning and thus provides an opportunity to correct errors and grow and improve their performance (Ribovica et al *, 2008 Karboki (2007) concluded in a study that errors are valuable indicators for detecting inconsistencies between It is suitable for external (environmental) conditions and characteristics and cognitive and motor abilities of people. Due to the limitations that exist in human abilities in dealing with various issues, the occurrence of errors in his performance is an undeniable fact and on the other hand Adhering to the philosophy of pure error prevention deprives human beings of the opportunity to learn, innovate and innovate. They presented the positive consequences of the error. (Kid & Fars, 2008) The goal of error prevention is to avoid the negative consequences of errors by avoiding available errors. (Sorio Harris, 2011) Therefore, error management emphasizes reducing the negative consequences of errors and increasing the potential positive consequences. Error management is an approach that tries to deal with the error and its negative consequences after the occurrence of the error. In addition, the error management approach claims that in this approach, errors are identified quickly, the negative consequences of errors are minimized and then learning Occurs (Fars , 2010) From the perspective of researchers, error management at the systemic (military) and organizational level can be applied using the concept of culture (Klein et al., 2004) Culture, a system of norms, common values and It is a set of common methods in the organization (Reacher and Schneider, 2000). So we can say that the culture of error management includes methods of communicating about errors in the organization, sharing knowledge gained from errors, seeking help in situations where errors can occur There is a quick detection and handling of mistakes that is applied with goals such as effectively dealing with the error and its effects and preventing future mistakes. (Edmundson, 2008) 10 in fact, knowledge gained from mistakes (a key element in organizations) and its sharing (Azmi et al., 2017 Cardoso et al., 2012) can be an important strategy in management decisions and achievement. To be most effective, the goal is to manage and share knowledge, achieve organizational goals, benefit from positive results in organizations (such as learning), increase organizational performance by designing and operating various systems, tools and cultures to share Sharing and using various types of knowledge is one of the important topics that has been in the focus of researchers in the field of management studies in recent years (Al-Qutuna et al., 2019 ; Budicherdella and Pamulapati, 2019 ; Holspel and Joshi, 2004 ; Manab and Aziz, 2019). Therefore, researchers and experts in the field of management believe that knowledge sharing as the most important processes in the structure of knowledge management in organizations has played an important role in creating and increasing self-efficacy motivation in managers and organizational staff. Aiming to spread knowledge in organizations and create knowledge judged have improved the knowledge sharing situation in organizations and organizational individuals and created a competitive atmosphere within the organization (between managers and employees of the organization)

and outside the organization competing with other organizations) (Abili et al., 2015, quoted by Ghaffari et al., 2017 ; Bakht et al., 2013). In the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, the need for learning in organizations such as educational organizations, which are faced with the challenge of rapid environmental change, problems and resulting errors, is strongly felt. It is necessary for any organization to take advantage of the errors resulting from knowledge gaps. That is why it is necessary to turn organizations such as educational organizations into environments that provide opportunities for their employees and clients to learn (jafar and Et al., 2019). Therefore, the question that is the main issue in this research is "What effect does the culture of error management have on organizational learning, considering the mediating role of knowledge sharing among the Academic staff?" ».

Due to the novelty of the research topic and considering the effects that error management culture can have on various aspects of employee performance in educational organizations (universities), we considered it necessary to investigate the impact of error management culture on employee organizational learning. Administrative and educational of Ardabil University, considering the mediating role of knowledge sharing in let's put the academic year 1399-1398. In this research, we try to be the founder of a university system through statistical analysis, concepts and principles and information obtained from statistical analysis, in which space for doing extraordinary work as well as creativity and innovative work and creating a safe job environment for education. And provide training for professors and administrative and educational staff, and also they have a sense of job security in their flame, trust and empathy and do not be afraid of mistakes in their responsibilities and observe the principle of reporting (knowledge sharing) to observe the culture of occupational safety Observance of this principle creates participatory behavior in educational organizations and increases synergy. The reasons that can lead to the need for this research and its novelty are:

1) This research is the first research to examine and analyzes the impact of error management culture on organizational learning of administrative and educational staff according to the mediating role of knowledge sharing in an academic environment.

2) This research can provide a new model for creating a culture of job security and error management in organizational activities in educational organizations.

3) Study and research on management skills and strategies to deal with mistakes in the organizational activities of administrative and educational staff shows the importance of training, skills and empowerment for educational organizations and the positions and functions of managers, so the need to study the issue is doubled. He does.

4) Organizational training and learning and all its principles and goals should be in line with the goals of the organization and the characteristics and needs of its employees. The existence of a culture of dealing with errors and a culture of safety can ensure this important thing.

The background of the research is a summary of the research conducted on the subject of the present study as follows:

Torchaghi and Mortazavi Amiri (2019) in a study on the study of organizational error management culture on knowledge sharing of employees of Tehran Region 4 and 5 concluded that Error management culture and its subscales have a positive and significant effect on employee knowledge sharing.

Seifollahi Gilande and Sattari in a study on the relationship between error management culture and organizational learning and innovation in the Ardabil General Directorate of Education concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between the variables discussed in the study.(Seifollahi Gilande and Sattari, 2016)

Moradi and his colleagues conducted a study on the mediating role of organizational learning in the impact of error management culture on organizational innovation in 2013 and concluded that error management culture has a positive effect on

organizational learning and innovation and it makes sense. Also, organizational learning in the impact of error management culture on organizational innovation plays the role of mediator and moderator (Moradi et al., 2013)

Moradi et al. (2012) in another study on the mediating role of knowledge acquisition capacity and its sharing on the relationship Between Learning from organizational errors and organizational innovation, it was concluded that knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on learning from organizational errors and also the direction of knowledge acquisition and sharing on the relationship between learning from organizational errors and organizational innovation has a mediating role Plays.

In a study, Mir Fakhreddini et al. (2010) concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between error management culture and organizational learning.

Hosseini Barani and Fatemi (2017, quoting Fathi Karkargh, 2020) in a study concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational wind culture and the concept of knowledge sharing in university staff in Iran.

Arati and Everett (2011) in a study conducted in educational organizations by designing a model for intra-organizational communication between employees about the errors occurred by them concluded that the use of this model (Error reporting) ends in organizational learning Regulates the reaction of employees to the occurrence of any human-organizational error or mistake. The state of education and learning in the organization (Arati and Everett, 2011)

Madsen and Desai (2010) in examining the subscales of culture of error (reporting) and knowledge sharing and their relationship with reducing organizational failures concluded that learning from previous organizational failures and observing its effects by sharing Knowledge becomes possible and has a significant effect on reducing organizational failures.

Carmeli (2007) concluded in a study that there is a positive and significant relationship between error management culture, social capital, psychological security and error-based learning behavior. Citkin (2006) in a study on the impact of error management culture on knowledge sharing and organizational performance concluded that the culture of high error management in organizations (Including the higher education system) will prevent errors, so that in these organizations people believe that they can always avoid the possibility of errors. Attempts to control the possible consequences of mistakes in the organization must be anticipated. Communicating about errors as the most important feature of error management causes errors to be announced to everyone immediately after they occur, thus making it possible for members and employees of the organization to be aware of each other's mistakes. This openness of communication Mistakes and shared understanding of potential error situations enable one to help others in such situations and quickly detect errors that lead to error correction and reduce the negative consequences of errors (Sitgin, 2006).

Van Dyke in a study Regarding the culture of error management in organizations, it was concluded that the culture of error management in organizations includes the reporting of functional errors, which control the negative results of errors and reduce it and provide windfall (Van Dyke, 2005, p. 1228)

According to the results of previous research and the subject of the research, the following conceptual model can be drawn for the present study.

Figure (1) - Conceptual model of research

2. Research Hypotheses

Error management on organizational learning is proven by the mediating role of knowledge sharing. Since no research has explored how and to what extent these three variables affect each other in an education organization, in this study we will examine the relationship between these three variables with each other. Based on this, the research hypotheses and questions will be as follows:

1) Error management culture has a positive and significant effect on the organizational learning of administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University, considering the mediating and moderating role of knowledge sharing.

2) The culture of error management has a positive and significant effect on the organizational learning of the administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University

3) Error management culture has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing of administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University

4) Knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on organizational learning of administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University

5) Status of error management culture and each what are its dimensions in the organization under study?

6) What is the status of knowledge sharing and each of its dimensions in the organization under study in the research?

7) What is the status of organizational learning and each of its dimensions in the organization under study in the research?

3. Research Method

In this research, the research method used is based on the purpose of the applied research (practical application of basic knowledge in a specific field) and based on the method of collecting descriptive (non-experimental) correlation (analysis of the relationship between variables based on the research objective). The statistical population of this study includes all the educational and administrative staff of the Islamic Azad University of Ardabil (400 people) who are working in 1399. The statistical sample is a subset of the whole community that represents it. The statistical sample of this research according to Morgan table includes 196 educational-administrative staff of Islamic Azad University, Ardabil Branch. The sampling method used in this research is a simple random sampling method in which all members have an equal chance to have a choice.

Data should be described quantitatively or qualitatively according to the various tools and methods available for data collection. , 2006, quoted by Fathi Karkarq, 2020) and the Knowledge Sharing Questionnaire (Dixon, 2001) and used.

The reliability of the fault culture questionnaire was evaluated by Mr. Hoffman et al. (2013) in a study in a hospital and it was found that this questionnaire has acceptable reliability¹². In fact, in this study, we used the equivalent questionnaire of this tool, which was translated and standardized by Shirinzadeh in a study, and its formal psychology was also approved by professors and experts in this field (Shirinzadeh, Islam, undated). We also did it and proved its face validity. Shirinzadeh used the Cronbach's alpha coefficient index of 13 to determine the equivalent version of this instrument, which considering that the calculated coefficient for the questionnaire is more than 0.7 the questionnaire has acceptable reliability (same source). The "error reporting process" is "continuous improvement" and "trust and confidence" and each area is measured with several items.

The Organizational Learning Questionnaire was designed by Pham and Svierszek (2006, quoting Fathy Karkargh, 2020) to assess organizational learning.. This questionnaire has 3 components and 12 items. The options were set according to the Likert five-choice range (from one meaning completely opposite to five meaning completely agreeable). Therefore, the total score of these 12 items will indicate the level of organizational learning. The total score (upper limit) of this questionnaire is equal to 60, the average limit is equal to 44 and the lower limit is equal to 12. This questionnaire has 3 subscales of knowledge acquisition (questions 1 to 5), knowledge transfer (6-7-8-9) and application of knowledge (questions 10-11-12). Also The study itself assessed the face and content validity of this tool as appropriate and obtained its reliability by Cronbach's alpha method higher than 0.7 (0.94).

In this study, to measure knowledge sharing, we used Dixon (2001) 15-item knowledge sharing questionnaire, which includes five dimensions of sequential knowledge sharing (questions 1 to 3), explicit (questions 4 to 8), hidden (questions 9 to 11).), Strategic (questions 12 to 13) and expert (questions 14 to 15), which is designed based on a 5-point Likert scale. The validity of the knowledge sharing questionnaire in Qelich Lee and Hakimi Tehran (2013) was 0.84, which indicates that the reliability of the pre-questionnaire is desirable.

4. Findings

According to statistical analysis, 64.3% (126 people) of the statistical samples are women and 35.7% (70 people) of the statistical samples are men. Most of the statistical samples of this study with 53 people (27.04%) have studied in the field of psychology. Most of the statistical samples of this study with 79 people (40.3%) have a bachelor's degree and the lowest number of statistical samples with 11 people (5.6 %) Have undergraduate education. 87.8% of the statistical samples of this research (172 people) are administrative staff and 12.2% (24 people) are faculty members. The average work experience of people is 8.2347 years and the highest work experience is 34 years and the minimum work experience is 1 year. People's data does not have a normal distribution in terms of work experience. 53.1% (104 people) of the statistical samples are single people and 46.9% (92 people) are statistical samples of married people. 97.4% (191 people) of the statistical samples are healthy people and 2.6% (5 people) Statistical examples include people with illness or disability. The average age of the people in this study is 34.5153 years and also the youngest person is 25 years old and the oldest person is 59 years old. Individual data have a relatively normal distribution in terms of age variables.

Table (1) - Calculation of Cronbach's alpha coefficient of three questionnaires

Name of the question	Cronbach alpha coefficients	Number of dimensions
Error management culture	0/78	7
Organizational Learning	0/85	4
Knowledge sharing	0/80	5

Results: Considering that the alpha coefficients in Table 4-13 are all close to one and the significance level is above 0.08, it can be said that all three questionnaires have acceptable reliability.

Main Hypothesis: The culture of error management has a positive and significant effect on the organizational learning of the administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University, considering the mediating and moderating role of knowledge sharing.

Results: According to the results of statistical analysis and Table (2), the impact factor of error management culture on organizational retaliation with respect to the mediating role of knowledge sharing (correlation coefficient) 3615. Has been obtained. Also, the level of significance in this hypothesis is 0.000, which is less than 05.0, so based on the results, it can be said that the correlation coefficient (impact) is significant and the culture of error management on organizational learning with respect to the mediating role of knowledge sharing it has a positive and significant effect.

Table (2) -The effect of error management culture on organizational learning of administrative and educational staff of Ardabil: University with respect to the mediating and moderating role of knowledge sharing

	Dependent variable	Input variable	Not standardized coefficients		Beta coefficient	T	The significance level	F	the amount of variance explained
			B	Standard error					
Check the first condition	Sharing knowledge	Fixed value of error management culture	73.593.78 1	13.2474 5	.554	20.576 9.274	0.000 0.000	86.006 Sig= 0.000	R ² =.307 justified R ² = .304
CHECK THE SECOND CONDITION	Organizational Learning	Fixed amount of knowledge sharing	.12043 .746	9.06200	.557	74.203 10.35	0.000 0.000	107.274 Sig= 0.000	R ² =.397 justified R ² = .353
	Organizational Learning	Fixed value of error management culture	58.028 1.227	11.4214 2	.696	13.517	0.000 0.000	F=192.697 Sig=0.000	R ² =.696 justified R ² = .485
	Organizational Learning	Fixed amount of error management culture and knowledge sharing	58.028 1.227	11.4214 2	.696	.203 16,068 10.357	0.000 0.000	F=182.697 Sig=0.000	R ² =.696 Justified R ² = .485

Table and conclusion is the necessary condition to prove the hypothesis, but the condition is not enough and to confirm it should use the sober test, which is practical according to the following formula:

$$S_{ab} = \sqrt{b^2 \cdot S_A^2 + a^2 \cdot s_b^2 + s_a^2 \cdot s_b^2}$$

b = non-standardized regression coefficient when the error management variable as The independent variable affects organizational learning as a dependent variable.

s_b = standard error b = non-standardized regression coefficient related to knowledge sharing when the variables of error management culture and knowledge sharing as an independent variable affect organizational learning as a dependent variable

s_a = standard error a s_b = standard error b finding: According to these findings (781. = b 11.42142 = s_b, 1.227 = a) by placing them in the formula of Sabel test, we came to the conclusion that z is equal to 9.251 and considering that the level of significance is less than 05.

It can be said that the culture of error management has a positive and significant effect on the organizational learning of Azad University staff due to the mediating role of knowledge sharing. . S = 13.24745 Sub-hypothesis:

Sub-hypothesis Error management culture has positive and significant effect on organizational learning of administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University.

Table (3) The effect of error management culture on organizational learning of administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University

Dependent variable	Variable Input)Independent	Not standardized coefficients		Standardized coefficient)Beta	T	significance level	F	the amount of variance explained
		B	Standard error					
Organizational Learning	Fixed value of error management culture	58.028 1.227	11.4214 2	.696	13.517	0.000 0.000	F=192 .697 Sig=0.000	R ² =.696 justified R ² = .485

Results: According to the results of statistical analysis and Table (3), the coefficient of effectiveness of error management culture on knowledge sharing (correlation coefficient) is / 697. Also, the level of significance in this hypothesis is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, so based on the results, it can be said that the correlation coefficient (impact) is significant and the culture of error management has a positive and significant effect on organizational learning.

Sub-hypothesis: Error management culture has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing of administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University.

Table (4) Investigating the effect of error management culture on knowledge sharing of administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University

Dependent variable	Variable Input)Independent	Not standardized coefficients		Standardized coefficient)Beta	T	The significance level	F	the amount of variance explained
		B	Standard error					
Sharing knowledge	Fixed value of error management culture	73.5 93.7 81	13.24 745	0/554	20.57 6 9.274	0.000 0.000	86/00 6 Sig= 0.000	R ² =.307 justified R ² = .304

Results: According to the results of statistical analysis and Table (4), the coefficient of effectiveness of error management culture on knowledge sharing (regression coefficient) is 551.. Also, the level of significance in this hypothesis is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, so based on the results, it can be said that the correlation coefficient (impact) is significant and the culture of error management has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing.

Sub-hypothesis: Knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on organizational learning of administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University.

Table (5) Investigating the effect of knowledge sharing on organizational learning of administrative and educational staff of Ardabil University

Dependent variable	Variable Input)Independent	Not standardized coefficients		Standardized coefficient)Beta	T	The significance level	F	the amount of variance explained
		B	Standard error					
Organizational Learning	Fixed amount of knowledge sharing	. 12043 .746	9.0620 0	74.203 10.35	.557	0.000 0.000	107.27 4 Sig= 0.000	R ² =.397 justified R ² = .353

Results: According to the results of statistical analysis and Table (5), the coefficient of effectiveness of knowledge sharing on organizational learning (regression coefficient) is 0/597 Also, the level of significance in this hypothesis is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, so based on the results, it can be said that the correlation coefficient (impact) is significant and knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on organizational learning.

Research questions: What is the status of error management culture and each of its dimensions in the organization under study in the research?

Explanation: To examine the current state of error management culture and each of its dimensions in the statistical population, we have used the One Sample T Test to test this hypothesis. Divide the scale and put the result as the average of each scale, and since the

questionnaire questions are based on the Likert scale of 7 options, we consider 4 as the average and the criterion and use it to calculate it.

$H_0 = \mu = A$ (unfavorable condition)

$H_1 = \mu \neq A$ (optimal condition)

Table (6) A review of the culture of error management and each of them in the staff of Ardabil Azad University

Dimensions	The significance level	middle limit (A)	Number of questions	Standardized average	the amount of T	Mean difference	number of samples
Error management culture	0/000	4	27	4/051	1/085	/0051	196
Communication feedback	0/000	4	3	4/120	24	0/120	196
Honesty in communication	0/000	4	5	4/027	5/4	0/027	196
balance and balance	0/000	4	5	4/094	18/8	0/094	196
Quality of reporting process	0/000	4	5	4/015	3	0/015	196
Continuous improvement	0/000	4	4	4/197	32/83	0/197	196
Trust and confidence	0/000	4	5	3/911	182/2	0/089	196

Results: The results of Table (6) show that the level of significance in all dimensions for the level of confidence is 0.95 less than 0.05. Also, the average obtained is higher than the average of the criterion (average). Error management culture and each of its dimensions are desirable in the statistical population under study.

Research questions: What is the status of knowledge sharing and each of its dimensions in the organization under study in the research?

Explanation: To examine the current state of knowledge sharing and each of its dimensions in the statistical population, we have used the One Sample T Test to test this hypothesis. First, the average of each subscale obtained by the number We divide the questions of that subscale and put the result as the average of each scale and considering that the questions of the questionnaire are based on Likert 5-point spectrum, consider 3 as the average and the criterion and calculate t from it.

$H_0 = \mu = A$ (unfavorable condition)

$H_1 = \mu \neq A$ (optimal condition)

Table (7) Investigating the status of knowledge sharing and each of its dimensions in the staff of Ardabil Azad University

Dimensions	Average (A)	Number of questions	Average	The significance level	The amount of t	Mean difference	number of samples
Sharing knowledge	3	15	2/730	0/000	6/651	0/286	196
Sequential knowledge	3	3	2/697	0/000	27/54	0/303	196
Explicit knowledge	3	5	2/821	0/000	10/368	0/197	196
Hidden knowledge	3	3	2/697	0/000	23/307	0/303	196
Strategic knowledge	3	2	2/716	0/000	31/5	0/284	196
Undergraduate knowledge	3	2	2/614	0/000	48/25	0/386	196

Results: According to the results of Table (7) that the average dimension is lower than the average (3) and considering that the level of significance in all dimensions is less than 0.05, so we can say that knowledge sharing and each of its dimensions it is not desirable in the statistical population under study

Research questions:

What is the status of organizational learning and each of its dimensions in the organization under study in the research?

Explanation: To examine the current state of organizational learning and each of its dimensions in the statistical population, we have used the One Sample T Test to test this hypothesis, first the average of each subscale on the number of questions we divide the subscale and put the result as the average of each scale. Considering that the questions of the questionnaire are based on the Likert scale of 5 options, we consider 3 as the average and the criterion and use it to calculate.

$H_0 = \mu = A$ (unfavorable condition)

$H_1 = \mu \neq A$ (optimal condition)

Table (8) A study of organizational learning status and each of its dimensions in the staff of Ardabil Branch of Azad University

Dimensions	Average (A)	Number of questions	Average	The significance level	The amount of T	Mean difference	number of samples
Organizational Learning	3	12	3/228	0/000	6/705	0/228	196
earn knowledge	3	5	3/276	0/000	69	0/276	196
knowledge transfer	3	4	3/209	0/000	52/25	0/209	196
Applying knowledge	3	3	3/3	0/000	75	0/3	196

Results: The results of Table (8) show that the level of significance in all dimensions for the level of confidence is 0.95 less than 0.05. Also, the average obtained is higher than the average of the criterion (average). Organizational Learning and each of its dimensions are desirable in the statistical population under study.

5. Discussion, Interpretation & Conclusion

This study examines and analyzes the mediating role of knowledge sharing in the impact of error management culture on organizational learning of academic staff, the results of statistical analysis show that the mediating role of knowledge sharing in the impact of error management culture on organizational learning of academic staff is positive and significant that This finding is in line with the results of studies by Alas and Wadi (2006) and Edvundson (2008). Their separate studies showed that the error management approach as a constructive and positive approach in the organization can lead to learning, innovation and sharing knowledge of errors (quoted by Tarchani and Mortazavi Amiri, 1398) In fact, this type of culture Due to its strategies and ways, it makes learning easier. On the other hand, this finding is based on the results of research by Egan et al. (2004), Moraus and Pourdan (2009, quoted by Moradi et al., 2013) and Docker (quoted From Shabani Arani et al., 2019) is also consistent As in the first two studies, it was found that the culture of error management has a positive and constructive role and effect on knowledge sharing and consequently knowledge absorption, Docker concluded in a study that the promotion and dissemination of error management culture in organizations, members Encourages knowledge sharing of errors and provides an opportunity for them to learn from errors.

Findings from statistical calculations of the first sub-hypothesis confirm the effect of error management culture on organizational learning, which is consistent with the findings of Van Dyke et al. (2005) and Abdolhian (2012, quoted by Fathy Karkargh, 2020). In fact, in his research, Abdullahian concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between error management culture, learning, innovation and organizational performance, and that organizational innovation plays a mediating role in the relationship between error management culture and organizational learning. Also, according to the studies of Van Dyke et al. (2005), with the establishment and development of error management culture in all organizational departments, organizational learning and knowledge transfer of organizational errors is improved.

Regarding the second sub-hypothesis of this research, the results of statistical analysis show that the culture of error management has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing. This finding with the results of studies by Terchani and Mortazavi Amiri (1398) and Van Dyke (2000; 2005) is consistent. In separate studies, they have emphasized the role and importance of error management culture in facilitating the process of organizational knowledge sharing, flexibility, learning and innovation.

The results of statistical analyzes related to the third sub-hypothesis show a positive and significant effect of knowledge sharing on organizational learning of university staff which can be similar to this effect in Zolanski's research (quoted by Moradi. et al., 2013) It can be seen that during his research on the relationship between knowledge sharing and absorption with organizational learning, he came to the conclusion that knowledge sharing and absorption is one of the important limitations in knowledge exchange between units of organizations under study. Was. He also concluded that knowledge sharing and absorption has a positive and significant relationship with organizational learning (Minbieva et al., 2003). This finding is also consistent with the findings of Edmundson and Mingeon (cited by Carnley and Schaefer, 2008, pp. 471-470) and Sitkin (ibid.). In separate studies on error management and organizational learning and knowledge sharing, they concluded that the relationship between these variables in

organizations leads to organizations being able to adapt more easily to conflicts and disturbances outside the organization (environment).

Based on the results, the answer to the first question can be stated that the situation of error management culture in the staff of Ardabil Azad University is favorable. This finding is in line with the results of the study of Moradi et al. (2013). Between the culture of error management and organizational innovation, they concluded that this relationship is positive and significant and the culture of error management has a favorable position in the statistical population. The findings of the second question of the research also show that the variable of knowledge sharing and its dimensions in the staff of Ardabil Branch of Azad University is in an unfavorable situation. This research finding is consistent with the research results of Feyz et al. (2017). Also, based on the findings of the third research question, it can be said that organizational learning and its dimensions are in good condition in the staff of Ardabil Branch Azad University. Vahidi (2017) is in line.

According to the obtained results and experiences during the research, it is suggested that the principle of "promoting, generalizing and developing the appropriate learning culture in all administrative-educational units of Ardabil Azad University" (coaching and coaching culture) be used as a strategy. And set a policy for its employees and document organizational information and knowledge for the use of employees, which requires the creation of a systematic information system to be able to organize, classify and access the information resulting from errors. In fact, according to Madsen and Desai (2010) research, in order to realize this proposal, it should be possible to create an atmosphere of trust and confidence among organizational employees so that they can have a positive view of each other's abilities, values and attitudes. The theory of Van Dyke et al. (2005) recommends creating free and strong communication channels for university staff to share experiences, information and skills. In this regard, it is important to establish a culture of error management in the organization. So that the reward system can be established for the interactions that errors between employees establish, in fact, based on the theory of Kenan and Edmundson (2005) and Karmeli (2007) can be acknowledged that the establishment of a culture of error management in the long run can lead to Improved organizational performance. In the discussion of study and research, with reference to the research of Lavo and Angai (2008), it can be recommended that more research be done in the field of knowledge sharing and organizational learning, as well as the factors affecting them in other organizations.

Each research has its own difficulties, shortcomings, obstacles and limitations according to the conditions under which it is performed. Also, the available sources and information are no exception to this, including the lack of direct and effective communication between the researcher and the subjects, which led to a decrease in the reliability and trust of the researcher in the raw data of the research. Also, organizational errors and understanding it to statistical samples was one of the challenges of the researchers in this study, so that some employees reacted negatively to some of the questions in the questionnaire and refused to answer the questions.

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